

REVIEW ARTICLE

A Performance Benchmarking Review of Transformers for Speaker-Independent Speech Emotion Recognition

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Speech Emotion Recognition (SER) is becoming a key element of speech-based human–computer interfaces, endowing them with some form of empathy towards the emotional status of the human. Transformers have become a central Deep Learning (DL) architecture in natural language processing and signal processing, recently including audio signals for Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) and SER. A central question addressed in this paper is the achievement of speaker-independent SER systems, i.e. systems that perform independently of a specific training set, enabling their deployment in real-world situations by overcoming the typical limitations of laboratory environments. This paper presents a comprehensive performance evaluation review of transformer architectures that have been proposed to deal with the SER task, carrying out an independent validation at different levels over the most relevant publicly available datasets for validation of SER models. The comprehensive experimental design implemented in this paper provides an accurate picture of the performance achieved by current state-of-the-art transformer models in speaker-independent SER. We have found that most experimental instances reach accuracies below 40% when a model is trained on a dataset and tested on a different one. A speaker-independent evaluation combining up to five datasets and testing on a different one achieves up to 58.85% accuracy. In conclusion, the SER results improved with the aggregation of datasets, indicating that model generalization can be enhanced by extracting data from diverse datasets.

Keywords: Speech emotion recognition; speaker-independent SER; cross-corpus SER; speech transformers.

1. Introduction

Emotion Recognition,¹ a subfield of affective computing, is situated within the broader domain of

Human–Computer Interaction (HCI).² Research on emotion recognition has been done exploiting diverse signal modalities, such as facial images,³ and

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ElectroEncephaloGraphy (EEG).⁴ In recent years, Speech Emotion Recognition (SER) has received significant attention due to its potential in improving remote voice-based interactive systems,⁵ i.e. interaction systems working over remote connections such as telephone or voice-based messaging systems. SER and emotional speech synthesis belong within the broader domain of speech signal processing, closely linked to Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) and Text-to-Speech (TTS) synthesis. These tasks intersect with multiple disciplines, such as modeling the function of the human phonation system,⁶ spectral feature processing,⁷ or prosody modeling.⁸

Both statistical Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques have been evaluated on the SER task⁵ following a methodology inherited from the general ASR area. In the application of ML techniques for SER, features used for classification are selected by system designers based on statistics or phonological properties. On the other hand, DL techniques carry out data-driven feature extraction processes, which often obtain more discriminant features in order to recognize patterns in the audio.

The main drawback of DL is the requirement of a large number of data samples. In the domain of SER, the number of utterances in available datasets is small, several orders of magnitude lower than the number required for robust training and validation, forcing the application of data augmentation techniques to enrich the dataset with synthetic samples that increase the pool of training data,⁹ or the use of transfer learning approaches in which a self-supervised pre-trained model can be fine-tuned over a new data domain to improve its performance.¹⁰ For transfer learning, it is convenient to select similar base and target domains to facilitate transfer of knowledge. For example, models for SER can be selected among models previously trained on ASR datasets. Other approaches produce synthetic data by the use of adversarial and generative learning. However, despite all these data enrichment procedures, models fail to generalize to a different context, e.g. other datasets or real-world dialogues,¹¹ without careful retraining in the target domain. Other important aspects of the datasets that impact the generalization capabilities of SER models trained over them include the techniques and quality of the

recordings, the demography and cultural group of the speakers, or their gender and age.

The main objective of this paper is to evaluate the current state of the development of speaker-independent models for SER. In other words, models that are independent of a specific training set so that they can be used in real-world situations outside laboratory environments. To this end, the following methodological steps have been undertaken:

- Identify pre-trained transformer models that achieve state-of-the-art accuracy after fine-tuning for the SER task.
- In order to assess generalization capability, evaluate these models after a SER fine-tuning, on a dataset different from the one used in training, thus containing new speakers unknown for the models.
- Combine various datasets to fine-tune new models with the goal of improving recognition accuracy for unseen speakers. Models are expected to capture shared features across multiple speakers, enhancing their generalization ability in emotion classification.

This paper is organized as follows: Sec. 2 provides an overview of the transformer architecture, highlights the most common audio transformer models, and summarizes the results achieved when these models are applied to the SER task. Section 3 details the methodology employed in this study, including the datasets used, the criteria for their selection, the computational tools employed, the fine-tuning process, and the design of the computational experiments. Section 4 presents the experimental results. Finally, Sec. 5 provides the general conclusions and suggests directions for future research.

2. Transformers

Transformers¹² were initially introduced in the area of Natural Language Processing (NLP). Combined with the self-supervised learning paradigm, they give rise to the foundational models and the Large Language Models (LLMs) that have revolutionized the field of Artificial Intelligence, extending them to other domains such as image, video and speech. Self-supervised learning is used to infer latent representations from unlabeled data, which later provide

excellent opportunities for subsequent fine-tuning in specific tasks.

The key component of the transformer model is the attention mechanism allowing the identification of long-range dependencies between the tokens in the input data stream, which are longer than those achieved by preceding techniques such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). In addition, the transformer model also captures the context in a more sophisticated way.¹³

The attention mechanism was already used as a complementary element in the design of RNNs, however, the transformer models improved the attention mechanisms and did not require the rest of the components that were part of an RNN. In the transformer model, attention is computed for every input token in a sequence through a multi-head mechanism where attention is computed in parallel with different learned projection matrices. The outputs of these heads are concatenated and linearly projected, allowing the model to jointly attend to information from different representation subspaces at different positions. In the original proposal, the multi-head attention consisted of eight parallel attention heads, though the number of heads is a hyperparameter that can be adjusted based on the specific application.

The transformer architecture includes two high-level components: The *encoder* and the *decoder*, which are assembled from elements such as embedding layers, positional encoders, multi-head self-attention mechanisms and feedforward neural networks. The transformer global attention is generated as follows: each output sequence element depends on all the terms in the input sequence and each preceding term in the output sequence.

2.1. Automatic speech recognition

Transformers have been successfully applied to the ASR task. Some of the most used and referenced models are the Wav2Vec¹⁴ family and its evolution Wav2Vec2.0.¹⁵ The Wav2Vec family consists of several models with different parameter sizes trained on different datasets. In these models, the audio signal is processed in consecutive time sliding windows of size 20ms with an overlapping of 5ms to provide connected continuity. First, the extracted

signal window is normalized in the $[0, 1]$ interval. Then, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) module transforms the data into a latent representation, which is convenient for further speech processing.

Another high performing model is Hidden-Unit BERT¹⁶ (HuBERT) which achieves an accuracy equivalent to Wav2Vec2 and sometimes higher. HuBERT defines a structure for the speech signal similar to the structure that BERT builds for natural (written) language. Windows of 25ms with overlapping of 5ms are used, but HuBERT does not perform a normalization of the signal data because it tries to maximize the information transfer to the model. Latent representations are generated from the speech windows, called *hidden units*, which are the elemental pieces used to build the language structure. These hidden units are clusters computed by a *K*-means algorithm whose quality is improved iteratively by a learning process.

In this study, we used and tested several pre-trained models based on Wav2Vec2¹⁵ and HuBERT¹⁶ that differ in the number of parameters and training datasets. For the sake of simplicity, we have assigned each model descriptive identifiers that are generally different from those usually applied in software repositories. The models used in this study are described as follows.

W2V2-B960¹⁵ is the BASE initial Wav2Vec2 model with 12 transformer blocks and 8 attention heads. Self-supervised pre-trained on 960 hours of the Librispeech dataset¹⁷ to learn speech representations and after that fine-tuned for ASR on Librispeech.

W2V2-L960¹⁵ is the LARGE initial Wav2Vec2 model with 24 transformer blocks and 16 attention heads. Self-supervised pre-trained on 960 h of the Librispeech dataset¹⁷ to learn speech representations and then fine-tuned for ASR on Librispeech.

W2V2-CV¹⁸ is a model fine-tuned on the CommonVoice dataset¹⁹ for multilingual phoneme recognition. It is based on one of the architectures proposed in the original Wav2Vec2 paper,¹⁵ with pre-training performed self-supervised on unlabeled audio from the LibriVox 60k hours portion of the Libri-light dataset.²⁰

W2V2-MD²¹ is a large model that underwent two training phases: initial pre-training self-supervised on unlabeled data from multiple domains (Librispeech,¹⁷ CommonVoice,¹⁹ Libri-Light²⁰ and Switchboard,²² and followed by fine-tuning on labeled data from Librispeech.¹⁷

W2V2-VP-B²³ is the BASE initial Wav2Vec2 model with 12 transformer blocks and eight attention heads but pre-trained self-supervised on the VoxPopuli dataset,²³ instead of Librispeech. VoxPopuli is a multilingual corpus widely used for various NLP tasks including speaker identification or recognition.

W2V2-VP-L²³ is the LARGE initial Wav2Vec2 model with 24 transformer blocks and 16 attention heads, pre-trained self-supervised on the unlabeled subset of VoxPopuli.²³

HuB-LL¹⁶ is the initial HuBERT model in its LARGE version with 24 transformer blocks and 16 attention heads. It was pre-trained self-supervised on unlabeled audio from the LibriVox 60kh portion of the Libri-light dataset.²⁰ No fine-tuning was performed on this model.

HuB-VP²⁴ using HuB-LL as the base model was fine-tuned on the VoxPopuli²³ speaker identification dataset.

HuB-ER²⁴ using HuB-LL as the base model was fine-tuned on the IEMOCAP²⁵ SER dataset.

HuB-Distil²⁶ is a distilled version of HuBERT that achieves a 75% reduction in model size. According to the authors, DistilHuBERT performs inference 73% faster than the original model while maintaining comparable performance. This efficiency gain also translates into reduced fine-tuning times.

2.2. Speech emotion recognition

There is no universally agreed-upon list of key emotions, but in the Artificial Intelligence context, the proposed model by Ekman,²⁷ comprising anger, fear, sadness, disgust, surprise, and happiness, is among the most widely accepted.²⁸ Ekman proposed that basic emotions are instinctive, expressed similarly across individuals in the same situations, and share

consistent physiological patterns. Nevertheless, intercultural studies challenge the universality of this model. Although there is a shared emotional basis, people tend to recognize emotions more accurately within their own cultural group, with sadness being the only emotion consistently recognized across cultures.²⁹ Comparative studies³⁰ show that languages can encode emotions differently, highlighting that emotional expression may be shaped by both physiological and sociocultural factors.

Emotions are deeply reflected in human physiology and behavior, influencing facial expressions, vocal tone, heart rate, and brain activity. Although facial expressions are commonly used for emotion detection, studies show that vocal cues may be more accurate, as people tend to identify emotions more precisely through voice alone.³¹ This is because the voice is harder to fake and conveys subtle emotional nuances. Physiological signals³² such as heart rate,³³ skin impedance, and respiration, are also useful for emotion recognition, with heart rate variability being particularly related to emotional states. Finally, EEG signals, which measure brain activity, are also widely used to detect emotions.⁴

Transformer architectures have been applied to emotion recognition over EEG signals³⁴ as well as to SER tasks. However, meaningful comparisons between approaches reported in the literature are challenging due to variations in both the subset of emotions analyzed and the specific transformer models employed. The following short review focuses on relevant works that closely align with the research reported in this paper, considering their choices of datasets, emotion categories, and transformer models. Table 1 summarizes the characteristics of the literature relevant to our own research.

Ziyang *et al.*³⁸ and Chen *et al.*³⁶ evaluate classifiers based on Wav2Vec2 and HuBERT models on SER datasets reporting state-of-the-art performance (both use SAVEE, only the former also use CREMA-D, CAFE, and TESS).

Chen *et al.*³⁶ discuss the use of Wav2vec2 for SER and explores various fine-tuning strategies to enhance its performance. The authors present baseline methods such as Vanilla Fine-Tuning (V-FT) and Task Adaptive Pre-Training (TAPT), and introduce a novel fine-tuning method called P-TAPT, which improves the model's ability to learn contextualized

Table 1. A comparative summary of transformer-based classifiers used for the SER task, specifying the datasets, number of emotions considered, and experimental accuracy results reported.

Research	Model	Dataset	# Emotions	% Accuracy
Luna-Jimnez <i>et al.</i> ³⁵	Wav2Vec2	RAVDESS	8	81.82
Chen <i>et al.</i> ³⁶	Wav2Vec2	SAVEE	6	86.70
Phukan <i>et al.</i> ³⁷	Wav2Vec2	TESS	6	84.76
Ziyang <i>et al.</i> ³⁸	Wav2Vec2	CREMA-D	6	61.95
Iyer <i>et al.</i> ³⁹	Wav2Vec2	CREMA-D	6	70.77
Bayraktar <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁰	HuBERT	RAVDESS	8	79.41
Ziyang <i>et al.</i> ³⁸	HuBERT	CAFE	7	59.50
Ziyang <i>et al.</i> ³⁸	HuBERT	SAVEE	6	71.91
Bayraktar <i>et al.</i> ⁴⁰	HuBERT	TESS	6	97.50
Ziyang <i>et al.</i> ³⁸	HuBERT	TESS	6	99.86
Ziyang <i>et al.</i> ³⁸	HuBERT	CREMA-D	6	75.83
Pastor <i>et al.</i> ⁴¹	HuBERT	Multicorpus	4	67.58

emotion representations, especially in low-resource settings.

Bayrakta *et al.*⁴⁰ apply several transformer models on several datasets (EmoDB, RAVDESS and TESS). Their main contribution concerns the pre-processing audio techniques applied to normalize and reduce the noise in the audio inputs. They report on state-of-the-art performance.

Iyer *et al.*³⁹ compare the results between Wav2Vec2 and AlexNet. They apply the classifiers to several datasets: RAVDESS, CREMA-D and IEMOCAP. The Wav2Vec2 model gets the best accuracy in this comparison but does not improve other state-of-the-art results achieved using CNN-based models.

Phukan *et al.*³⁷ also perform a comparative study of several techniques. In this case, they used general ASR models and speaker identification models and compared the results on four datasets (CREMA-D, TESS, SAVEE and EmoDB). The better performance is achieved by the speaker identification models. They concluded that the information already present in the models to identify the speaker could help to recognize emotions.

Luna-Jimnez *et al.*³⁵ apply a Wav2Vec2-based transformer model pre-trained with 53 languages to recognize emotions in a multi-modal data context on the RAVDESS dataset. The best results were achieved by tuning the model to this specific task and adding a multi-layer perceptron behind the transformer. The accuracy was 81.82% taking into account the eight emotions offered by this dataset.

Pastor *et al.*⁴¹ study how cross-corpus strategies for data augmentation can be used to provide more samples to unbalanced datasets, that is, how to complete classes with a lower number of samples. They used IEMOCAP as the base dataset and added samples from the EmoDB⁴² and RAVDESS datasets, with German and English utterances, respectively. Both SVM and HuBERT-based models are analyzed. This paper is an example of aggregating utterances from different datasets.

3. Methodology

A key consideration in this study was the selection of the spoken language. Given the abundance of English-language datasets and the necessity of integrating multiple sources, English was chosen as the target language for the computational experiments in this paper. As discussed in Sec. 2.2, emotional expression is not universally encoded across cultures; therefore, addressing multicultural SER lies beyond the scope of this work. Our current focus is on speaker-independent SER for English speakers in Western countries. For emotion classification, the objective was to include a broad set of emotions commonly addressed in the literature. Although a reduction in the number of emotion classes could potentially yield improved performance metrics, it would also restrict the generalization potential and depth of the findings. The following sections detail the methodological choices implemented in the experimental design.

3.1. Selection of datasets

Publicly available SER data presents several challenges. Although the volume of SER datasets has expanded in recent years, it remains significantly smaller than that available in other domains. SER datasets are often characterized by a limited number of samples, primarily consisting of acted emotions performed by professional actors, rather than spontaneous dialogues. This discrepancy poses significant challenges to the accurate recognition of emotions, as spontaneous emotions are inherently more difficult to discern than acted ones.¹¹ Moreover, SER datasets exhibit substantial heterogeneity in key aspects, including variations in the subset of the emotions included, unbalanced samples; reduced representation or absence of certain emotions, or both, are common. Similar inconsistencies exist with respect to the duration of the speech and semantic content. To mitigate these limitations, six datasets were selected for this study, prioritizing those with a similar emotion set and the broadest range of speakers and expressions. Even with English as the target language, two datasets recorded in other languages were included to explore their potential to contribute to the improved generalization across datasets. Ideally, we would have used spontaneous rather than acted expressions, but the scarcity of spontaneous data makes unfeasible to use them for training (fine-tuning) and validation, especially when we try to assess the effect of dataset aggregation. Future work should aim to incorporate spontaneous emotions. All datasets used in the computational experiments are described as follows.

3.2. Datasets

The RAVDESS⁴³ (Ryerson Audio-Visual Database of Emotional Speech and Song) is a multi-modal database that comprises 7356 audio and video clips. The emotional audio dataset contains 1440 samples of speech audio recordings, which are recorded by 24 professional actors (12 male and 12 female) that read two semantically neutral US English phrases while revealing eight emotions (neutral, calm, happiness, sadness, anger, fear, disgust, surprise). Each utterance is pronounced on two levels of emotional intensity (only one intensity in neutral emotion).

The SAVEE⁴⁴ (Surrey Audio-Visual Expressed Emotion) multi-modal database consists of 480

utterances from four English male actors in seven emotions (anger, disgust, fear, happiness, neutral, sadness, surprise). The sentences were selected to include 15 phonetically balanced sentences per emotion: three common for all emotions, two emotion-specific, and ten generic sentences for each emotion (the common and emotion-specific sentences were recorded in neutral emotion).

The Toronto Emotional Speech Set⁴⁵ (TESS) dataset consists of 200 utterances from phrases with controlled syntactic, lexical and phonological properties spoken by an older female speaker and a younger female speaker to convey seven emotions (anger, disgust, fear, sadness, neutral, happiness, pleasant surprise).

The CREMA-D⁴⁶ (Crowd-Sourced Emotional Multi-modal Actors Dataset) is a dataset that consists of facial and vocal emotional expressions in sentences spoken in a range of six emotions (happy, sad, anger, fear, disgust, neutral). It comprises 7442 clips by 91 actors (48 male and 43 female) of various ethnic backgrounds (Caucasian, African American, Hispanic and Asian). The actors were between 20 and 74 years old and read 12 sentences, each rendered in all emotional states.

The EMOFILM⁴⁷ dataset is a multilingual emotional speech corpus comprising 1115 audio instances produced in English, Italian and Spanish languages. The audio clips were extracted from 43 films. Five emotions were considered: Anger, contempt, happiness, fear and sadness.

The Canadian French Emotional⁴⁸ (CAFE) dataset contains six different French sentences, pronounced by six male and six female actors, in seven emotional states (anger, disgust, happiness, fear, surprise, sadness, neutral). Each basic emotion is spoken in two different intensities (only one for neutral).

3.3. Computational tools

Several open-source libraries and public-domain resources have been used to conduct the experiments. The basic libraries for deep learning tools were PyTorch and CUDA. All pre-trained transformer models and datasets are publicly available in the HuggingFace⁴⁹ repository. Regarding hardware, we used the infrastructure of the Super-computing

and Visualization Center of Madrid,⁵⁰ in our case mainly using V100 and A100 GPU's.

3.4. Fine-tuning and experimentation process

A series of computational experiments were conducted to evaluate the speaker-independent performance of the models. The fine-tuning, validation, and test subsets were generated once for each dataset and remained fixed throughout all experiments to ensure consistency. Stratified sampling was applied to maintain a proportional representation of each emotion in the subsets, where 80% of the utterances were used for fine-tuning, with 10% reserved for validation during fine-tuning, and the remaining 10% for final testing. Each model was fine-tuned for 20 epochs, with training repeated five times. The learning rate was set to 10^{-5} and the weight decay to 10^{-3} . After each epoch, the model with the best validation performance was saved. The final results report the average test accuracy across the five runs. The experimental design pipeline is illustrated in Fig. 1 and it is described as follows:

- Initial model comparison: The first step involves fine-tuning and the independent evaluation of all models using only the RAVDESS dataset, which is the most balanced with respect to speakers and

features. The six models that perform best in this experiment will be selected for the next phase.

- Comprehensive independent validation: Each selected model from the previous step is fine-tuned on each of the six datasets alone, providing reference values for the next experiments. At the end of this phase, the model with the lowest accuracy will be discarded and the five remaining will be used in the following experiments.
- Feasibility of dataset aggregation: This experiment evaluates whether combining multiple datasets creates undesirable interactions that degrade model performance. Fine-tuning is carried out on the six datasets aggregated in one, with training, validation, and test splits containing stratified samples drawn from all constituent datasets. The expected result is that the accuracy should remain consistent and comparable to the results obtained in the previous experiment, which used individual datasets in isolation.
- Speaker-independent evaluation on single datasets: The next step is to evaluate how well the remaining five models perform, after being fine-tuned on a single dataset, when classifying utterances from the other datasets, which is a speaker-independent evaluation. This experiment provides a baseline for the last one with respect to speaker-independent performance.

Fig. 1. Experimental pipeline diagram.

- Speaker-independent evaluation on aggregated datasets: In this final phase, the five models will be fine-tuned on a mix of samples from different datasets and tested on utterances from a dataset not used during the training process, i.e. independent speakers.

4. Experimental Results

4.1. Initial model comparison

The ten models described in Sec. 2.1 were evaluated in this preliminary experiment. For this first classification, the RAVDESS dataset was selected because of its well-balanced distribution of emotions and speakers compared to the others. As explained above, each model was fine-tuned for 20 epochs, five times, with a stratified split of 80/10/10. The results are the mean of the five test accuracies of each model, presented in Table 2. These results will serve as the basis for model selection in the following phases of the experimental pipeline. In general, HuBERT models outperform the Wav2Vec2 family with only two exceptions. We expected HuB-ER to be near the top as it includes an additional emotional fine-tuning

Table 2. Initial classification after 20 epochs on the RAVDESS dataset.

Model	Mean accuracy
HuB-ER	95.10%
HuB-LL	93.01%
W2V2-L960	90.87%
W2V2-VP-B	90.53%
HuB-VP	90.21%
HuB-Distil	89.62%
W2V2-CV	89.48%
W2V2-B960	89.46%
W2V2-MD	88.42%
W2V2-VP-L	83.50%

on IEMOCAP.²⁵ We expected that the models trained on the VoxPopuli dataset for speaker recognition²³ also perform among the best due to some results reported in the literature,³⁷ however this improvement is not clear in our results. For the following experiments, we discard four models, keeping the six best performers.

4.2. Comprehensive independent validation

The fine-tuning is carried out on each dataset individually for 20 epochs five times, with the stratified split already mentioned. The results are summarized in Table 3, revealing that the performance of the models is very similar, comparing well with the highest benchmarks reported in the state of the art presented in Table 1. No model consistently outperformed the others across all datasets; the accuracy level is more related to the dataset itself. Among models, given a fixed dataset, accuracies tend to perform in order similarly to the behavior of the previous step with little exceptions. In particular, datasets with greater speaker diversity, such as CREMA-D and EMOFILM, yielded the lowest accuracy values, as expected. The last column of the table, named average, shows the mean value of all the accuracies per model along the six datasets, and it has been used to order the models in this table according to its average performance across datasets. To add an initial view of performance per emotion, two confusion matrices for HUB-LL fine-tuned on RAVDESS and CREMA-D are shown in Fig. 2, we can see that for RAVDESS the hardest emotion to classify is sadness, while in the case of CREMA-D, sadness and disgust are similarly harder to classify than the rest of emotions.

Since the original HuB-LL model serves as the base for the HuB-VP and HuB-ER models, comparing these three models provides insight into

Table 3. Performance of models on each dataset and the averaged accuracy.

Model	RAVDESS	SAVEE	TESS	CREMA-D	EMOFILM	CAFE	Average
HuB-ER	95.10%	91.67%	100%	78.01%	84.30%	89.89%	89.93%
HuB-VP	90.21%	92.70%	100%	77.94%	82.96%	90.96%	89.13%
W2V2-L960	90.87%	89.58%	100%	79.08%	82.06%	88.83%	88.40%
HuB-LL	93.01%	90.62%	100%	80.49%	78.47%	86.17%	88.13%
W2V2-VP-B	90.53%	82.29%	100%	76.67%	78.02%	84.04%	85.26%
HuB-Distil	89.62%	83.33%	100%	72.69%	72.19%	85.10%	83.82%

RAVDESS								CREMA-D						
	neutral	happy	sad	angry	fear	disgust	surprise	neutral	happy	sad	angry	fear	disgust	
neutral	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	93.5%	2.8%	1.9%	0.9%	0.9%	0.0%	
happy	0.0%	94.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	5.3%	1.6%	90.6%	0.0%	3.9%	3.1%	0.8%	
sad	15.8%	0.0%	78.9%	0.0%	5.3%	0.0%	0.0%	12.6%	3.1%	63.0%	1.6%	17.3%	2.4%	
angry	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.8%	5.5%	0.0%	85.8%	3.1%	4.7%	
fear	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	94.7%	0.0%	5.3%	3.1%	4.7%	13.4%	0.0%	78.0%	0.8%	
disgust	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	5.3%	0.0%	94.7%	0.0%	2.4%	6.3%	11.8%	4.7%	7.1%	67.7%	
surprise	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	5.3%	0.0%	5.3%	89.5%							

Fig. 2. Confusion matrices from single fine-tuning.

whether the previous fine-tuning for specific tasks influences current performance. In addition, it will be possible to compare HuBERT and Wav2Vec2 architectures. By a narrow margin, HuB-Distil is excluded from further evaluation; however, we note that HuB-Distil was significantly faster during training and inference, making it a strong candidate for deployment in real-life systems. Furthermore, the distillation techniques used to create HuB-Distil could be applied to optimize other models in future work. The other five models will be compared in all remaining experiments.

4.3. Feasibility of dataset aggregation

The next question that has been experimentally assessed is: What is the effect of combining multiple datasets without any adaptations? We must confirm that utterances from different domains do not interfere with each other during training, making their combination without adaptations unfeasible.

To investigate this research question, the CAFE, CREMA-D, EMOFILM, RAVDESS, SAVEE, and TESS datasets were aggregated into a unified dataset. The fine-tuning, validation and testing subsets were obtained by combining the respective initial splits of each individual dataset, ensuring consistency with previous experimental setups and the correct balance of emotions among subsets. Again, five rounds per model along 20 epochs, 80/10/10 stratified splits with the same hyper-parameters as in every case.

Table 4 presents the performance results on the five remaining models. The accuracy is consistent between them and compared with that of the previous experiment in Table 3. The absence of observed incompatibility between the datasets supports the continuation of the experimental process.

4.4. Speaker-independent evaluation on single datasets

The next experiment tried to give some answer to the question: How well does a model fine-tuned on one dataset classify data from an unseen dataset? This setup represents a speaker-independent evaluation. To test this, each of the five models previously fine-tuned on individual datasets was evaluated on the remaining datasets. Table 5 presents the accuracy scores for all combinations of training-testing. The results show a significant performance drop when the models are applied to different datasets: For example, models fine-tuned on RAVDESS show accuracy drops ranging from 35 up to 65 points when tested on

Table 4. Aggregation feasibility.

Model	Accuracy
HuB-ER	85,73%
HuB-LL	84,98%
W2V2-L960	83,71%
W2V2-VP-B	82,78%
HuB-VP	85,33%

Table 5. Testing each model against each dataset different from the one used on fine-tuning. All combinations.

Test dataset	RAVDESS	SAVEE	TESS	CREMA-D	EMOFILM	CAFE
Fine-tuned with RAVDESS						
HuB-ER	—	46.88%	26.43%	39.00%	33.63%	56.91%
HuB-VP	—	42.71%	26.43%	30.06%	26.01%	57.98%
W2V2-L960	—	55.21%	44.00%	45.86%	40.81%	58.51%
HuB-LL	—	52.01%	40.71%	44.92%	40.81%	56.92%
W2V2-VP-B	—	36.46%	22.68%	34.10%	38.56%	43.62%
Fine-tuned with SAVEE						
HuB-ER	47.72%	—	46.79%	37.05%	26.46%	45.21%
HuB-VP	33.68%	—	33.00%	33.89%	16.14%	35.64%
W2V2-L960	46.67%	—	39.00%	28.45%	30.01%	39.36%
HuB-LL	44.91%	—	38.00%	39.21%	28.69%	37.24%
W2V2-VP-B	26.67%	—	36.00%	27.90%	24.66%	20.21%
Fine-tuned with TESS						
HuB-ER	41.75%	25.00%	—	33.64%	17.94%	32.98%
HuB-VP	45.96%	46.88%	—	35.52%	19.73%	33.51%
W2V2-L960	34.74%	23.96%	—	33.09%	24.22%	30.00%
HuB-LL	35.79%	25.00%	—	26.63%	17.04%	30.86%
W2V2-VP-B	39.65%	23.96%	—	29.05%	22.87%	31.91%
Fine-tuned with CREMA-D						
HuB-ER	41.40%	47.92%	48.36%	—	44.84%	35.51%
HuB-VP	44.91%	52.08%	53.21%	—	39.01%	41.49%
W2V2-L960	42.11%	35.42%	42.00%	—	37.67%	44.15%
HuB-LL	47.72%	35.42%	41.43%	—	43.05%	42.02%
W2V2-VP-B	29.12%	26.04%	47.86%	—	38.12%	31.38%
Fine-tuned with EMOFILM						
HuB-ER	20.00%	12.50%	15.71%	30.33%	—	29.26%
HuB-VP	28.77%	13.54%	22.14%	35.04%	—	30.32%
W2V2-L960	21.05%	13.54%	15.71%	31.67%	—	21.81%
HuB-LL	26.67%	9.38%	19.46%	33.76%	—	31.91%
W2V2-VP-B	25.26%	14.58%	20.18%	29.99%	—	30.32%
Fine-tuned with CAFE						
HuB-ER	42.11%	64.58%	25.36%	41.62%	44.84%	—
HuB-VP	54.04%	53.13%	25.36%	33.82%	37.67%	—
W2V2-L960	63.16%	53.13%	40.36%	28.71%	45.29%	—
HuB-LL	55.44%	57.29%	33.75%	42.77%	42.60%	—
W2V2-VP-B	53.68%	38.54%	28.99%	31.67%	35.43%	—

other datasets (as seen in Table 3). Similar patterns occur in all cases. These drops are attributed to dataset-specific biases related to limited speaker diversity, scripted content, demographics, and recording conditions, which cause models to overfit to the characteristics of the original dataset.

Table 6 was generated from Table 5 by combining the accuracies achieved with respect to the datasets. The first column shows the average of all the values obtained fine-tuning with a given dataset and gives a

Table 6. Average accuracy achieved when a dataset is used for fine-tuning versus for testing.

	As fine-tuning	As independent testing
RAVDESS	41.65%	39.72%
SAVEE	34.50%	36.21%
TESS	30.47%	33.32%
CREMA-D	41.29%	34.31%
EMOFILM	23.32%	32.64%
CAFE	42.93%	37.96%

measure of the dataset generalization capabilities; for example, models fine-tuned on RAVDESS got an average accuracy of 41.65%. The second column shows the average of all the accuracy values obtained when a dataset is used as an independent testing dataset. This gives a measure of the emotional implicit features that a dataset shares with the rest of the datasets, which in the case of RAVDESS is 39.72%.

The analysis reveals the following key insights on the generalization capabilities of each model fine-tuned on specific datasets on unseen utterances:

- The models fine-tuned on RAVDESS, CREMA-D and CAFE achieve the best overall performance when classifying data from different datasets. They offer implicit features that are useful for increased generalization power.
- Models fine-tuned on SAVEE, TESS, and EMOFILM achieve the worst overall performance when classifying data from different datasets. EMOFILM is the dataset with the lowest number of emotions, which clearly limits its generalization contribution. The SAVEE and TESS cases are related with the number of different speakers they have, having the fewest number of different speakers, which also limits their generalization contribution.
- As test sets, TESS, EMOFILM and CREMA-D are the hardest to classify by models fine-tuned on different datasets. Note that CREMA-D and EMOFILM include a wider range of speakers, and EMOFILM has three languages and some background noise, so it is necessary a wide variability in the fine-tuning sources.
- A particular case is TESS. Despite the models achieving the highest accuracies on itself, these models show poorer generalization compared to models fine-tuned on other datasets. TESS has only two actresses, but has the highest ratio of utterances per speaker, therefore, it is too specific. As a consequence, it quickly drives models to overfit and offers poor generalization when trying to classify different speakers.
- Another particular case is CAFE, especially since it is the smallest of the six datasets and is in French. The models derived from it are the best for classifying the other datasets. Also, it is the second least difficult to classify from others, therefore we

may infer that it shares many implicit features with the rest of datasets. We expected that a different language might be an obstacle to model generalization. However, our results confirm that emotions are not codified just in the language, cultural nuances shared between speakers, even when using a different language, are much more relevant. As we discussed in Sec. 2.2, a full universal code for emotions in speech is difficult to accept, but CAFE is not just French, it is Canadian French, its speakers are also native bilingual in English and quite culturally close to the US English speakers.

4.5. *Speaker-independent evaluation on aggregated datasets*

The final research question addressed in the experiments is as follows: Do the results for classifying unknown speakers improve if the model is fine-tuned with multiple aggregated datasets? To answer this question, the models were fine-tuned on some combinations of the datasets, and the fine-tuned models were tested on unseen utterances from an additional dataset.

To evaluate the generalization of the models, one dataset was reserved as the target for validation, and the remaining five were used for fine-tuning in different combinations. CREMA-D was chosen as the target because it encompasses the broadest variety of speakers and is therefore considered to represent real world scenarios more closely. Furthermore, preliminary experiments on one dataset alone revealed that CREMA-D is the most challenging dataset, as evidenced by the results in Table 3. For all five models evaluated in that previous experiment, the lowest classification accuracies were consistently observed for CREMA-D.

Table 7 provides a comprehensive summary of the results, including single-dataset accuracies from Table 5 and accuracies achieved with models fine-tuned on incremental combinations of datasets aggregated and tested on CREMA-D. As in this case, testing and fine-tuning are performed with different datasets and there are no splits, the process is different. All models were trained for 20 epochs, 5 rounds and testing was performed on the complete CREMA-D dataset after each epoch, keeping the best value per round. The reported values

Table 7. Performance of each model fine-tuned with single and aggregated datasets tested on the CREMA-D dataset.

Training datasets	Models				
	HuB-ER	HuB-LL	W2V2-L960	W2V2-VP-B	HuB-VP
RAVDESS	39.00%	44.92%	45.86%	34.10%	30.06%
SAVEE	37.05%	39.21%	28.45%	27.90%	33.89%
TESS	33.64%	26.63%	33.09%	29.05%	35.52%
CAFE	41.62%	42.77%	28.71%	31.67%	33.82%
EMOFILM	30.33%	33.76%	31.67%	29.99%	35.04%
RAVDESS + SAVEE	52.68%	52.02%	50.54%	44.77%	49.24%
RAVDESS + SAVEE + TESS	53.88%	53.88%	46.96%	43.60%	53.25%
RAVDESS + SAVEE + TESS + CAFE	56.60%	56.42%	50.05%	44.46%	55.27%
RAVDESS + SAVEE + TESS + CAFE + EMOFILM	58.85%	56.40%	51.74%	45.86%	55.48%

correspond to the average test accuracy of the five rounds. There is also a view of performance per emotion in Fig. 3, with two confusion matrices for the case of fine-tuning HuB-ER and HuB-LL on five aggregated datasets. Both models present similarities with respect to the hardest emotions to classify, happy, angry, and particularly fear and disgust. If we compare now with the initial CREMA-D matrix in Fig. 2, we can see that the model on aggregated datasets surprisingly gets better performance for sadness than the initial CREMA-DE model, meaning that the aggregation gathered enough implicit features to improve on this emotion. However, the rest of emotions are below in the aggregated than in the initial one, as expected, particularly for fear and disgust, so there is margin of improvement for future works. One last comment, as the aggregation included the emotion surprise, but CREMA-D does not have this emotion, so the models assigned some utterances to

the surprise emotion. This misclassification is minor compared with others because it is the column with fewer assignments. The main error in the confusion matrix comes from the happy emotion, which is not far in expression to surprise. This result is encouraging, taking into account that that the models did not see samples from CREMA-D during fine tuning.

The results indicate that the models fine-tuned on aggregated datasets demonstrate improved performance compared to those fine-tuned on single datasets. Notably, HuBERT-based models exhibit a consistent performance enhancement with increasing dataset aggregation. In contrast, Wav2Vec2-based models show less consistent gains, with the improvement not as linearly progressive with dataset accumulation. The HuB-ER model slightly outperformed its base HuB-LL, which is consistent with its original fine-tuning on the IEMOCAP SER dataset.²⁵ However, the HuB-VP model performed

		HuB-ER									HuB-LL							
		neutral	happy	sad	angry	fear	disgust	surprise			neutral	happy	sad	angry	fear	disgust	surprise	
neutral -		77.6%	4.8%	13.0%	0.5%	0.4%	3.6%	0.3%		neutral -		63.5%	5.2%	25.5%	0.5%	1.0%	4.3%	0.1%
happy -		9.0%	59.3%	5.5%	2.4%	5.3%	7.6%	10.9%		happy -		7.1%	52.5%	5.9%	3.1%	5.0%	10.1%	16.3%
sad -		16.2%	1.4%	72.5%	0.1%	3.7%	5.7%	0.4%		sad -		9.9%	2.0%	69.9%	0.0%	10.3%	7.2%	0.6%
angry -		6.9%	14.4%	1.0%	56.4%	3.7%	13.9%	3.6%		angry -		6.4%	13.5%	1.0%	55.2%	2.0%	13.9%	8.0%
fear -		6.5%	9.6%	33.4%	2.1%	39.1%	4.6%	4.8%		fear -		3.4%	10.9%	27.6%	2.0%	42.6%	4.2%	9.4%
disgust -		6.2%	6.5%	29.3%	2.4%	4.8%	50.2%	0.6%		disgust -		4.1%	7.4%	22.0%	2.2%	6.4%	55.5%	2.4%

Fig. 3. Example confusion matrices obtained after fine tuning over five datasets aggregated. Left, confusion matrix for the HuB-ER model. Right, confusion matrix for the HuB-LL model.

marginally worse than HuB-LL, despite fine-tuning of the VoxPopuli dataset.²³ These findings do not provide further support for the hypothesis that speaker identification datasets contribute to SER improvement, as suggested by Phukan *et al.*³⁷ Similarly, W2V2-VP-B, pre-trained on unlabeled VoxPopuli data,²³ did not demonstrate any exceptional SER capabilities. Finally, the maximum accuracy reported in Table 6 (i.e. 58.85%) approaches the previous state-of-the-art values for CREMA-D, as presented in Table 1, although it remains lower than the accuracies computed on each dataset separately as shown in Table 3.

4.6. Insights learned from dataset aggregation

There are several aspects related to the benefits of aggregating datasets for the improvement of SI-SER. In the case of deep learning, small datasets limit the capacity of models to extract features from data. In our experiments, we have increased the volume of samples from a range between 100 and 2800 samples to a range between 5000 and 12,000 samples. This difference in dataset size also implies that a small dataset suffers from corpus-specific biases (e.g. homogeneous demographics, controlled recording conditions, single gender, limited age range). Models trained on single datasets often memorize individual speakers rather than learning general features of emotions. Let us review in more detail some of these aspects:

- **Diversity-Driven Generalization:** Aggregating datasets increases speaker diversity across demographics, accents, languages, and vocal characteristics. This expanded representation helps models learn emotion-invariant features that generalize across different vocal manifestations, rather than overfitting to specific speakers present in individual datasets.
- **Recording Condition Robustness:** Individual datasets typically use consistent recording setups, microphones and acoustic environments across all its samples. Aggregation exposes models to varied recording conditions, acoustic environments, and audio quality levels, forcing the model to learn features resilient to technical variations rather than memorizing dataset-specific artifacts.
- **Annotation Methodology Compensation:** Different datasets employ varying annotation

schemes, labeling criteria, and emotional taxonomies or different intensities per emotion. Aggregation can help models learn from multiple perspectives on emotional categorization, potentially capturing more nuanced boundaries and reducing biases from individual annotation approaches.

- **Statistical Power and Rare Pattern Detection:** Larger aggregated datasets provide more statistical power to detect subtle emotion-speech relationships that might be noise in smaller datasets. This is particularly important for emotions that have more subtle acoustic signatures
- **Implicit Ensemble Learning:** Training on aggregated data may implicitly create an ensemble effect, where the model learns multiple complementary representations of emotions from different data sources, leading to more stable and accurate predictions.
- **Domain Adaptation Through Exposure:** Exposure to multiple datasets during training naturally builds domain adaptation capabilities, making the model more flexible when encountering new speakers or recording conditions during inference.

These effects may be synergistic rather than simply additive, creating a threshold effect where sufficient diversity enables qualitatively better emotion representation learning. This needs further investigation in the following works in this line of research. In summary, emotions are expressed through complex spectral patterns that can also exhibit significant local dilation and compression on the time axis depending on the speaker and context, so greater exposure to aggregated datasets helps models learn more robust and truly speaker independent features, rather than overfitting to the specific characteristics of a single limited dataset.

5. Conclusions and Further Work

This study has presented an extensive evaluation of the Wav2Vec2 and HuBERT model families for the task of SI-SER, using six datasets in various combinations. First, we fine-tuned several pre-trained models on each of the datasets; CAFE, CREMA-D, EMOFILM, RAVDESS, SAVEE and TESS, achieving or surpassing the recent state-of-the-art results reported in Table 1. Then we conducted

exhaustive experiments from the obtained models to evaluate how they perform when classifying utterances from datasets not included in the fine-tuning phase, revealing a generalized performance drop, with accuracies below 40%. Finally, we fine-tuned multiple models on combinations of different datasets and evaluated them on unseen data, confirming that the results improved with the aggregation of datasets. For example, testing on CREMA-D after fine-tuning on the aggregation of the other five datasets increased accuracy to 58.85%. This demonstrates that generalization can be improved by extracting features from diverse datasets, highlighting the importance of data diversity to build robust and generalizable models.

5.1. Future work

The primary obstacle to speaker-independent emotion recognition is the availability of enough data to allow robust generalization. An important avenue for future work is the creation of datasets designed for speaker-independent recognition in real-world applications. Such datasets should encompass a wider range of characteristics, including background sounds, more speakers, a greater variety of emotional utterances, and spontaneous rather than acted expressions.

With respect to models and architectures, a deeper understanding of the role of different layers of transformers in emotion classification is necessary. This knowledge could be used to optimize fine-tuning for the SER task and, quite important, could also help to explain the classification performed by the transformer. In emotion-sensitive domains, interpretable is crucial for deployment, especially in clinical or affective computing contexts. Furthermore, since pre-training plays a significant role, a valuable line of research would be to explore training models from scratch with specifically designed architectures and using data that better capture features relevant to SER.

The possibility of embedding SER systems into multimodal systems, such as EEG-based emotion recognition, that have reached the interactive performance level⁵¹ or those based on electrodermal signals⁵² is another way to achieve speaker independent emotion recognition systems overcoming the shortage of robust training data. EEG-based

emotion recognition has been also demonstrated on low-cost equipments,⁵³ which makes them compatible with voice-based systems.

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